

Gemini Science

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Gemini Observatory achieved its first science observations in July 2000, when it targeted the Galactic center from Maunakea using the adaptive optics instrument Hokupa'a, then on loan from the University of Hawai'i. Thus, this year we are celebrating 20 years of science with the Gemini telescopes. Here we highlight a few of the more recent scientific results from Gemini, including a high-dispersion study of evolved exoplanet hosts, the discovery of the most energetic quasar outflow observed to date, and the first colorful glimpse

of Earth's fleeting mini-moon. The objects targeted in these programs were brought to light by the Kepler mission, the Sloan Digital Sky Survey, and the Catalina Sky Survey. These stories therefore illustrate the enormous potential for synergy between wide-field sky surveys and fast, flexible, large-aperture facilities such as Gemini. They also presage some of the key science we anticipate from Gemini during its third decade of operations, as we begin a new era of synergy with the Vera C. Rubin Observatory.

Figure 1: Small portions of the high-resolution Gemini/GRACES spectra of the early-stage red giants Kepler-391 and Kepler-278, both of which host multiple confirmed transiting exoplanets. Various lines used in deriving chemical abundances, effective temperatures, and surface gravities are labeled. (Reproduced from Jofré et al. 2020, A&A, 634, A29)

Insight into Exoplanets around Red Giants

NASA's *Kepler* mission monitored over 150,000 stars for four years and yielded over 4760 exoplanet candidates, about half of which have been confirmed, and new searches of the *Kepler* database by independent teams continue to turn up additional candidates. The vast majority of the exoplanet hosts lie on the main sequence, but *Kepler* also monitored over 16,000 stars on the red giant branch (RGB). Other things being equal, one might expect the yield of transiting exoplanets around RGB stars to be in the hundreds, and detailed studies of these could constrain models of planet-star interaction in evolved systems.

However, of course, other things are not equal for red giants. The stars' large sizes (which decrease the depths of transits) and irregular variabilities make detecting planetary transits much more difficult. As a result, only 0.1% of the observed red giants have confirmed planets found by *Kepler*, and only three of these stars are known to host multiple transiting exoplanets. A recent study, led by Emiliano Jofré of the Observatorio Astronómico de Córdoba, uses new high-quality, high-resolution Gemini GRACES data to derive stellar parameters and chemical abundances of 25 elements for two of the three known multi-planet RGB systems. Portions of the GRACES spectra for these stars, Kepler-278 and Kepler-391, are shown in Figure 1.

Both of the stars were observed for the full four years of the *Kepler* primary mission. Kepler-278 hosts two Neptune-sized planets with periods of 30 and 51 days, while Kepler-391 hosts two somewhat smaller planets with periods of 7.4 and 21 days. Analysis of the GRACES data, combined with *Gaia* parallaxes, indicates that the stars are near twins, with temperatures of 5000 K, radii three times that of the Sun and masses 25% larger than the Sun's; for Kepler-278, this is 15% lower than previous estimates of its mass. The study finds that both stars are spectral type K2 III-IV with ages close to 5 Gyr, and both are just beginning to ascend the RGB. However, Kepler-278 has a metallicity about 1.6 times the solar value, compared to 1.1 times solar for Kepler-391.

The new high-quality measurements of the stellar parameters allow for refined analyses of the *Kepler* light curves, enabling improved estimates of the exoplanet properties and better characterization of their orbits. In particular, for the Kepler-278 system, the study confirms the presence of transit timing variations (TTVs) for the outer planet Kepler-278c and detects for the first time the TTV signal for the inner planet as well. This makes possible the first measurements of the masses of these planets, 56 and 35 Earth masses for Kepler-278b and Kepler-278c, respectively. No TTVs were detected in the Kepler-391 system, so only upper limits on the planetary masses could be derived. The analysis indicates that the orbits of the Kepler-278 planets are coplanar and surprisingly eccentric, which could have resulted from a sudden mass loss event by the host star, but precise radial velocity follow-up is needed to confirm the high eccentricities.

As these two stars continue to ascend the RGB, all four of their known planets are expected to be engulfed. Studies of larger samples of planets around evolved stars, including those further along the RGB, are needed to constrain scenarios for planet-star interaction in such systems. The *TESS* mission will observe hundreds of thousands of red giants and should provide a much larger sample of transiting exoplanets for detailed high-resolution follow-up studies.

Fathoming the Outflow in an FeLoBAL

Gas heating via energetic feedback from active galactic nuclei has become the semi-analytic modelers' go-to mechanism for halting star formation in massive galaxies. One way to probe the physics of this phenomenon in the real universe is through broad absorption line (BAL) features in quasar spectra. The large blueshifting of the absorption is clear evidence of rapidly outflowing material. Broadly speaking, quasars with such features can be divided into those that show broad absorption by only highly ionized species (HiBAL) and those that also show it for

Figure 2: Spectrum of the quasar SDSS J1352+4239, showing the “overlapping trough” of low-ionization iron absorption characteristic of such FeLoBAL quasars. The spectrum is a composite of BOSS data at optical wavelengths and Gemini/GNIRS and APO/TripleSpec data in the infrared. Key features are marked. The strong H α line observed at 2.14 μ m provides the redshift, which was difficult to constrain precisely from the optical because of the broad absorption and lack of strong emission features. (Reproduced from Choi, Leighly, Terndrup 2020, ApJ, 891, 53)

low-ionization lines (LoBAL). A subclass of the latter are the FeLoBAL quasars, which show broad Fe II absorption. While the outflows in some HiBALs have velocities near 20% the speed of light, outflows in the rarer FeLoBALs have higher column densities and can be more energetic. However, blending of the numerous broad Fe II features creates a major challenge to extracting the physical properties of the outflows.

A new study led by graduate student Hyunseop Choi of the University of Oklahoma uses the novel spectral synthesis code *SimBAL* to analyze the outflow of material in the FeLoBAL quasar SDSS J1352+4239. The data, shown in

Figure 2, are a combination of an optical spectrum from the Baryon Oscillation Spectroscopic Survey (BOSS) and infrared spectra obtained with the Gemini Near-Infrared Spectrograph (GNIRS) at Gemini North and the TripleSpec instrument at the Apache Point Observatory. The prominent H α line observed in the IR data provides an unambiguous redshift of $z = 2.264$, which is higher by 0.23 than previously reported from optical data alone. The *SimBAL* code, developed by Karen Leighly (University of Oklahoma) and Donald Terndrup (Ohio State), performs Bayesian forward-modeling of quasar spectra to constrain the physical parameters of the outflowing gas. The code is

designed especially for quasars with blended BAL features, such as the “overlapping trough” of Fe II lines evident in the rest-frame UV spectrum of SDSS J1352+4239.

Based on the detailed spectral modeling, the study derives outflow velocities reaching 38,000 km/s, with a velocity width of about 10,000 km/s. This is the highest outflow velocity ever measured for an FeLoBAL. The black hole mass estimated from the H β line is 8.6 billion solar masses, which means that SDSS J1352+4239 is radiating near its Eddington limit, with an inferred mass accretion rate of 176 solar masses per year. In comparison, the estimated mass outflow rate exceeds 3000 solar masses per year, and the momentum flux of the outflow exceeds that of the quasar photons by a factor of twenty. This can be explained by the presence of dust, which would scatter the photons and could serve as an accelerating mechanism for the outflowing material.

The authors conclude that the outflow in SDSS J1352+4239 is the most energetic found to date. The energy flux easily exceeds the threshold required for quasar feedback to be an efficient means of quenching star formation in the surrounding galaxy. The team is currently analyzing a larger sample of FeLoBAL quasars to determine the distribution of their outflow properties and how SDSS J1352+4239 fits within the larger population.

Welcoming a New Neighbor

Dynamical models of the Solar System predict that meter-sized asteroids are captured roughly once per year into temporary orbits by our planet; for asteroids 3m in size, it’s about once per decade. Such objects, that make at least one complete revolution around the Earth, are called temporarily captured orbiters (TCOs). More colloquially, at least since the discovery of 2020 CD3 hit the press in late February this year, they are known as “mini-moons.” They are extremely difficult to detect because they not only are tiny by astronomical standards but also move the fastest along their plunging geocentric orbits when they are at their closest and brightest.

On 15 February of this year, astronomers Kacper Wierzos and Teddy Pruyne at the University of Arizona’s Catalina Sky Survey detected a rapidly moving near-Earth object that observations on the following night confirmed to be on a geocentric orbit. Originally designated C26FED2, the object’s motion over the next week showed no evidence of perturbation due to solar radiation pressure; thus, its area-to-mass ratio was consistent with that of an asteroid, rather than a misplaced hunk of debris from Earth’s space program. In addition, integration of the orbit backwards in time revealed no associations with past space missions. These results strongly supported a natural origin for the object, which would make it only the second TCO discovered while in geocentric orbit. The previous one, 2006 RH120, also found by the Catalina Sky Survey, orbited for a bit over a year before escaping.

The international Gemini Observatory received a Director’s Discretionary Time proposal from a team led by Grigori Fedorets of Queens University Belfast to observe the mini-moon candidate, still going by the moniker C26FED2 at time. The program was approved and rapidly made ready on 23 February; the resulting observations, shown in Figure 3, were obtained later that night. At the time of discovery, the object was at 0.7 lunar distances, headed outward from a closest approach of only 0.12 lunar distances two days earlier. By the time of the Gemini observations, it was already at 2.4 lunar distances and almost 3 magnitudes fainter than at discovery. On 25 February, in view of the evidence favoring a natural origin, the International Astronomical Union’s Minor Planet Center bestowed the formal designation, 2020 CD3. Analysis of the multi-band Gemini data will enable broad classification of the asteroid type.

Although we hardly got to know it, 2020 CD3 departed Earth orbit by May 2020 and won’t drift our way again until 2044. However, more mini-moons are in the pipeline—specifically, they will be in the moving object pipeline of the Vera C. Rubin Observatory. Estimates for the number of TCO discoveries by Rubin Observatory vary between ~ 1 per month and ~ 1 per year, depending mainly on the exact

cadence of the observations and the efficiency of confirmation. Most will be only tens of centimeters in size. Follow-up of these TCOs by Gemini and other large facilities can reveal their surface compositions and constrain the origin of the smallest objects in the inner Solar System. Discoveries of mini-moons with long capture durations would also provide easy targets for retrieval missions, perhaps of an entire meter-sized asteroid.

Figure 3: This crisp little dot amongst the colorful star trails is the temporarily captured object 2020 CD3, more popularly known as Earth's latest "mini-moon." It was observed with GMOS at Gemini North in the early morning hours of 24 February 2020. The color image is a composite of six 5-minute non-sidereally tracked exposures in the g,r,i filters. (Credits: The international Gemini Observatory/NOIRLab/NSF/AURA/G. Fedorets/Queen's University Belfast)